

EFFECT OF FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL QUALIFICATION ON THEIR STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

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Abstract

Professional qualification of teachers refers to the knowledge, skills, and competencies that teachers acquire through formal education and training programs. It has a critical role in shaping teachers' effectiveness, instructional practices, and ultimately, student. To find the impact of female secondary school teachers' professional qualification on students' academic achievement in secondary schools within the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Khyber The sample comprised 238 female teachers of district Haripur at secondary school level. In addition, two strata were selected. From each stratum, only female teachers were selected randomly. Urban (67 female) and rural (171 female) by using proportionate stratified random sampling. Keeping in view the research question of the study, data was analyzed quantitatively using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics through SPSS software. Students taught by teachers with B.Ed 4-year show significantly higher academic achievement compared to all other PQ categories. Because this professional program is the most comprehensive degree of Education, in Pakistan. It is proved through this study that the teachers equipped with B.Ed 4-year, have the capability to performed better than all other PQ categories, in secondary school examinations in terms of student academic achievement. Teachers with B.Ed. 4-year professional qualification significantly impact student academic achievement as compared to other professional qualification programs.

Keywords: Students' Academic Achievement. Teachers' Professional Qualification

INTRODUCTION

Ongoing research continues to explore the impact of professional qualification on teachers' performance and the quality of education they provide. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) examined the relationship between teachers' professional qualifications and student achievement across multiple countries. The findings revealed that teachers with higher levels of education and specialized training in their subject areas had a positive impact on student learning outcomes. The study emphasized the importance of rigorous and comprehensive teacher preparation programs in equipping teachers with the necessary knowledge and skills to meet the diverse needs of students.

Teachers' professional qualification serves as a vital foundation for effective teaching. According to Bonney et al. (2015) teachers with advanced degrees and specialized training are better equipped to deliver high-quality instruction. They possess a deep understanding of subject matter, pedagogical strategies, and curriculum development, which enables them to design and implement engaging and effective lessons.

Additionally, research by Smith et al. (2021) has shown that professional qualification of teachers positively correlates with the academic achievement of the students, as qualified teachers tend to have a stronger command of instructional techniques, leading to improved learning outcomes. Furthermore, research by Ingersoll and Strong (2011) explored the influence of teachers' credentials and qualifications on their job satisfaction and retention. The study highlighted those teachers with stronger professional qualifications, such as advanced degrees and certifications, reported high scores for job satisfaction effect on retention the teaching profession. This suggests that professional qualifications not only contribute to teachers' effectiveness but also influence their overall job satisfaction and career longevity.

Timperley et al. (2017) examined effect of sustained professional qualification development on teachers' instructional practices and academic achievement of students. Moreover, the incorporation of technology into teacher education programs has gained significant attention. Research by Buss et al. (2015) explored the integration of technology as a component of teachers' professional qualification. The study highlighted the importance of preparing teachers to effectively use technology in their instruction, as it has the potential to enhance student engagement, critical thinking, and collaboration.

In summary, teachers' professional qualification, including their educational background, specialized training, and ongoing professional development, is crucial for their effectiveness in the classroom. The latest research consistently supports the positive impact of professional qualifications on teacher performance in terms of academic achievement of students. By investing in comprehensive teacher preparation programs, promoting continuous professional development, and integrating technology effectively, educational stakeholders can enhance teachers' professional qualifications and ultimately improve the quality of education provided to students.

Professional qualification holds immense importance in the teaching and learning process. It refers to the knowledge, skills, and competencies that teachers acquire through formal education, specialized training, and ongoing professional development. The importance of professional qualification can be understood in several key aspects:

- **Enhanced Pedagogical Knowledge:** Professional qualification equips teachers with a strong foundation of pedagogical knowledge. Through their education and training, teachers gain a grasp of effective instructional strategies, curriculum development, techniques used for assessment, and management of classroom. This knowledge enables them to plan and deliver engaging lessons, cater to diverse student needs, and create optimal learning environments.
- **Subject Matter Expertise:** Professional qualification ensures that teachers possess a strong command of the subjects they teach. In-depth knowledge of the content enables teachers to provide accurate and comprehensive instruction, facilitate meaningful discussions, and address students' questions and misconceptions. Subject matter expertise also fosters teachers' credibility, allowing them to guide students towards deeper understanding and higher levels of achievement.

- **Effective Instructional Practices:** Professional qualification empowers teachers to employ evidence-based instructional practices. Teachers with professional qualifications are well-versed in research-supported teaching methods, differentiated instruction, and the use of instructional technologies. They can implement diverse instructional strategies, adapt to various learning styles, and promote active engagement and critical thinking among students.
- **Individualized Student Support:** Professional qualification equips teachers with the skills to support the diverse needs of students. Through their training, teachers learn about student development, cultural competence, and strategies for differentiation and inclusion. They can identify individual strengths and challenges, provide personalized support, and create inclusive learning environments where every student can thrive.
- **Continued Professional Growth:** Professional qualification emphasizes the importance of ongoing professional development. Qualified teachers recognize the need for continuous learning and stay updated with advancements in pedagogy, curriculum, and educational research. They actively engage in professional development opportunities, reflect on their practice, and refine their instructional approaches to meet evolving student needs.
- **Positive Impact on Student Outcomes:** The importance of professional qualification is reflected in its direct impact on student outcomes. Research consistently demonstrates a positive correlation between teachers' professional qualification and student achievement. Teachers who possess strong professional qualifications are more likely to facilitate student learning, promote higher levels of academic performance, and contribute to students' holistic development.

In conclusion, professional qualification is of utmost importance in the teaching profession. It enhances teachers' pedagogical knowledge, subject expertise, instructional practices, and individualized student support. Through ongoing professional development, qualified teachers continually refine their skills and adapt to the changing needs of students. Ultimately, professional qualification positively impacts student outcomes, promoting optimal learning experiences and fostering students' academic success and overall well-being (Khurshid, 2008).

Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) examined the relationship between teachers' qualifications and student achievement across multiple countries. The research highlighted that teachers' professional qualifications, including advanced degrees and specialized training, positively correlated with student learning outcomes. Teachers who possessed higher levels of professional qualification demonstrated better instructional practices, subject expertise, and student engagement, leading to improved academic achievement.

Furthermore, a meta-analysis by Hattie (2009) synthesized over 800 studies and identified the effect sizes of various factors influencing student achievement. The research revealed that teachers' professional qualification, as indicated by their subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, and experience, had a significant impact on student

learning. Teachers with strong professional qualifications were found substantial positive effect on academic achievement across different levels and subjects. Numerous studies have examined the impact of teachers' professional qualification on student outcomes, providing valuable insights into this relationship.

The research consistently supports a positive relationship between the professional qualification of teachers and students' academic achievement. Teachers with stronger professional qualifications, such as higher levels of education, subject-specific training, and specialized expertise, are associated with improved student outcomes. These findings emphasize the significance of investing in comprehensive teacher preparation programs, ongoing professional development, and the promotion of specialized knowledge and skills to enhance the professional qualification of teachers and ultimately benefit student achievement.

The efficacy of teachers is strongly correlated with the calibre of their training, which should be both pertinent and adapted to the talents and abilities of the mentors and trainers engaged, as well as the accessibility of training resources, according to Kruijer (2010). According to Myung et al. (2013), emphasis should be given to the teachers' existing level of certification, the use of face-to-face tutoring components, and ongoing monitoring when offering training to improve teacher credentials. However, the distance between training facilities and schools' locations frequently presents a problem. Face-to-face training sessions are frequently criticised by trainees as being overly crowded, too brief, and lacking in interaction. Additionally, the material created for professional development courses targeted at enhancing teacher qualifications does not necessarily correspond with the unique requirements of educators.

Significant efforts have been made in Pakistan to guarantee the calibre of teacher preparation programs, including both pre-service and in-service settings. This project has benefited greatly from the implementation of updated teaching standards. Offering opportunities for professional development to instructors of all levels of expertise has been the focus. The hiring of highly skilled teachers with considerable expertise has been given priority to improve the quality of education. To assist in-service professional growth, the government built several teachers training facilities, including the Provincial Institute of Teacher Education (PITE). To meet the unique demands of future teachers, specialised primary teaching institutes have been formed. The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Directorate of Elementary and Secondary Education (ESE) actively takes part in in-service teachers' professional development.

In Pakistan, due to lack of relevant jobs opportunities, students with medical, engineering and IT backgrounds are also applying for the post of SSTs (secondary school teachers). Due to which most of the seats were taken by academically strong candidates instead of those who have strong professional profile with professional degree of teaching like B.Ed 1-year, 1.5-year, 2.5-year, 4 years, M.Ed 1-year. When both types of teachers come into classroom, one with strong academic qualifications and one with strong professional qualification, they undoubtedly make a difference in terms of: Students' achievement; Teaching skills and techniques; Job satisfaction and creating learning environment in the classroom.

The impact of teachers' professional qualification on students' academic achievement at the secondary school level is a significant area of concern within the education system. Despite the recognition of the critical role teachers play in student learning outcomes, limited research has specifically examined these variables and their interrelationships in the context of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Therefore, this study aimed to address the following problem:

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has a unique educational landscape with diverse cultural, linguistic, and socio-economic backgrounds, which may influence the dynamics between teachers and students. Despite efforts to improve the quality of education, the region faces challenges in terms of academic performance and student outcomes. Therefore, understanding the relationship between teachers' professional qualification and student achievement is essential for designing evidence-based interventions to enhance educational practices and improve student outcomes.

Firstly, the level of teachers' professional qualification within secondary schools in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa requires investigation. It is important to understand the extent to which teachers possess advanced degrees and specialized training in their respective subject areas. Finding the relationship between professional qualification of teachers and academic achievement of their students shed light on the significance of educational credentials in ensuring quality teaching within the region. By addressing this specific research problem, this study would contribute to filling the existing gap in knowledge regarding the impact of teachers' professional qualification on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. This research study was delimited to, Government Secondary School in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, and Female Secondary School Teachers.

RESEARCH QUESTION

By keeping in view, the scarcity of literature, the research questions of the study were:

What is the effect of teachers' professional qualification on students' academic achievement at secondary school level?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Quantitative non experimental causal comparative research methodology was selected to find effect of teachers' professional qualification on students' academic achievement, based on several factors that align with the research question like generalizability, statistical analysis, and efficient data collection, and standardization, time, and resource considerations.

Population and Sample

The population of research comprised of all secondary level teachers in District Haripur, Pakistan. The 51 female high schools, female high school teachers are 738 females. In addition, urban (02 female), semi-urban (09 female) and rural (40 female) high school teachers. The total population of teachers in each stratum urban (199 female) and rural

(539 female). The sample comprised 238 female teachers of district Haripur at secondary school level. In addition, two strata were selected. From each stratum, only female teachers were selected randomly urban (67 female) and rural (171 female) by using proportionate stratified random sampling. The sample drawn from the population based on 5% confidence level.

Data Collection Tool

A research questionnaire was developed to collect data from sampled female secondary teachers. In demographic section respondents were asked about their professional qualifications. In other section they asked about subject wise and class wise SSC Board Results with detail total students appeared, fail, pass and if pass how many got A+, A, A-, B+, B, B-, C+, C, C-, and D+, D, D-.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Collected data were analyzed quantitatively through SPSS software. The results of data analysis were represented as follows:

Table 1: Professional qualification of the teachers

Level	N	% age	Cumulative % age
No Professional Qualification	6	2.5	2.5
B.Ed (1-year)	74	31.1	33.6
(1.5-year)	124	52.1	85.7
(2.5-year)	15	6.3	92.0
(4-year)	6	2.5	94.5
M.Ed (1-year)	13	5.5	100.0
Total	238	100.0	

Table 1 displayed the professional qualification of teachers as 74(31.1%) teachers were B.Ed (1-year), 124(52.1%) were B.Ed (1.5-year), 15(6.3%) were B.Ed (2.5-year), 6(2.5%) were B.Ed (4-year), while 13(5.5%) were M.Ed (1-year). And only 6(2.5%) teachers were there who didn't have any professional qualification.

Table 2: Student academic achievement (SAA) against teacher professional qualification (PQ)

PQ	Mean	N	SD
No Professional Qualification	56.62	6	2.53
B.Ed (1-year)	37.54	74	8.36
B.Ed (1.5-year)	53.48	124	11.41
B.Ed (2.5-year)	68.66	15	6.75
B.Ed (4-year)	69.64	6	12.36
M.Ed (1-year)	58.94	13	15.55
Total	50.27	238	14.12

Table 2 shows the student academic achievement (SAA) against teacher professional qualification as teachers (74) with B.Ed (1-year) have 37.54 mean value while Std. Deviation was 8.36. Similarly, SAA against teachers (124) with B.Ed (1.5-year) have 53.48 mean value while Std. Deviation was 11.41, and teachers (15) with B.Ed (2.5-year) have 68.66 mean value while Std. Deviation was 6.75, and teachers (6) with B.Ed (4-

year) have 69.64 mean value while Std. Deviation was 12.36, while teachers (13) with M.Ed (1-year) have 58.94 mean value while Std. Deviation was 14.12. Teachers (6) with no professional qualification have 56.62 mean and 2.53 Std. Deviation.

Table 3: Effect of professional qualification on student academic achievement using ANOVA test

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	21814.411	5	4362.882	39.769	.000
Within Groups	25451.967	232	109.707		
Total	47266.377	237			

Table 3 shows the results of ANOVA test as if there are significant differences in student academic achievement based on the professional qualification of the teachers. The F-statistic of 39.769 indicates that there is a significant difference in academic achievement among the groups. The associated p-value (Sig.), which is extremely low (0.000), suggests that this difference is highly statistically significant.

Table 4: Post-Hoc for effect of professional qualification on student academic achievement

(I) PQ	(J) PQ	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
No PQ	B.Ed (1-year)	19.076*	4.446	0.000
	(1.5-year)	3.136	4.378	0.475
	(2.5-year)	-12.044*	5.059	0.018
	(4-year)	-13.022*	6.047	0.032
M.Ed (1-year)	B.Ed (1-year)	-2.326	5.169	0.653
	B.Ed (1.5-year)	-15.941*	1.538	0.000
	(2.5-year)	-31.121*	2.966	0.000
	(4-year)	-32.098*	4.446	0.000
B.Ed (1.5-year)	B.Ed (1-year)	-21.403*	3.150	0.000
	B.Ed (2.5-year)	-15.180*	2.863	0.000
	(4-year)	-16.157*	4.378	0.000
	M.Ed (1-year)	-5.462	3.053	0.075
B.Ed (2.5-year)	B.Ed (4-year)	-0.977	5.059	0.847
	M.Ed (1-year)	9.718*	3.969	0.015
B.Ed (4-year)	M.Ed (1-year)	10.695*	5.169	0.040

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 4 presents the results of post-hoc tests for the effect of professional qualification (PQ) on student academic achievement, following the significant findings obtained from the ANOVA test. According to Post-Hoc for effect of professional qualification on student academic achievement, it was concluded that teachers with no professional qualification, were performed better than teachers with B.Ed 1-year and B.Ed 1.5-year. But the performance of teachers with B.Ed 2.5-year, B.Ed 4-year and M.Ed 1-year have better performance in terms of students' academic achievement as compared to the teachers with no professional qualification.

- The performance of teachers with B.Ed 1-year was lower than the teachers with professional qualification of B.Ed 1.5-year, B.Ed 2.5-year, B.Ed 4-year and M.Ed 1-year.
- The group of teachers with professional qualification of B.Ed 1.5-year, also have low performance in respect of student academic achievement, as compared to the group of teachers with professional qualification of B.Ed 2.5- year, B.Ed 4-year and M.Ed 1-year.
- The group of teachers with professional qualification of B.Ed 2.5-year, has better performance than the teachers with M.Ed 1-year, but has low performance than teachers with B.Ed 4-year professional qualification.
- The group of teachers with B.Ed 4-year, has the best performance in terms of student academic achievement as compared to all other groups of teachers having other PQ (B.Ed 1-year, B.Ed 1.5-year, B.Ed 2.5-year and M.Ed 1-year).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following conclusions were drawn based on findings of the study:

- i. Teachers with No PQ: Students taught by teachers with "No Professional Qualification" show significantly higher academic achievement as compared to PQ categories of B.Ed 1-year and B.Ed 1.5-year.
- ii. B.Ed 1-year Qualified Teachers: Students taught by teachers with "B.Ed 1-year" show significantly low academic achievement compared to all other PQ categories (B.Ed 1.5-year, B.Ed 2.5-year, B.Ed 4-year and M.Ed 1-year).
- iii. B.Ed 1.5-year Qualified Teachers: The students taught by the teachers with "B.Ed 1.5-year" have better results than the PQ category of B.Ed 1-year. But have significantly low academic achievement compared to other PQ categories (B.Ed 2.5-year, B.Ed 4-year and M.Ed 1-year).
- iv. B.Ed 2.5-year Qualified Teachers: Results suggests that students taught by B.Ed 2.5-year qualified teachers tend to have significantly higher academic achievement compared to those taught by B.Ed 1-year and B.Ed 1.5-year qualified teachers. But have significantly low academic achievement compared to other PQ categories (B.Ed 4-year and M.Ed 1-year).
- v. M.Ed 1-year Qualified Teachers: Students taught by teachers with "M.Ed 1-year" show significantly higher academic achievement compared to all other PQ categories except B.Ed 4-years.
- vi. B.Ed 4-year Qualified Teachers: Students taught by teachers with "B.Ed 4-year" show significantly higher academic achievement compared to all other PQ categories. Because this professional program is the most comprehensive degree of Education, in Pakistan. On the basis of findings of the study, it is proved that the teachers equipped with B.Ed 4-year, have the capability to performed better than all other PQ categories, in secondary school examinations in terms of student

academic achievement. Teachers with B.Ed 4-year professional qualification significantly impact student academic achievement. The findings further emphasize the importance of teacher professional qualification in relation to student outcomes specifically the importance of B.Ed 4-year program is highlighted.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the findings of your study regarding the impact of different teacher professional qualifications on student academic achievement, the following recommendations can be made:

- **Teacher Professional Qualification Enhancement:** It is evident from study that teacher professional qualification has a significant impact on student academic achievement. Therefore, educational institutions and policymakers should focus on enhancing the professional qualification of teachers. This can be achieved by encouraging teachers to pursue advanced degrees such as B.Ed 4-year, 2.5-year and 1.5-year programs.
- **Promotion of Comprehensive Teacher Training:** The study highlights the superiority of the B.Ed 4-year program in terms of its impact on student achievement. Institutions should consider promoting and investing in comprehensive teacher training programs like B.Ed 4-year. These programs should not only cover subject matter expertise but also pedagogical skills, classroom management, and student-centered teaching approaches.
- **Evaluation and Selection of Teachers:** Educational institutions should consider the findings of your study when evaluating and selecting teachers. Prioritizing teachers with higher professional qualifications, particularly B.Ed 4-year, can lead to improved student outcomes. This can also involve redesigning teacher recruitment processes to give preference to candidates with more comprehensive training.
- **Research and Longitudinal Studies:** This study has provided valuable insights, but it would be beneficial to conduct further research and longitudinal studies to track the long-term impact of different teacher qualifications on student achievement. This can help provide a more comprehensive understanding of how teacher qualifications influence student outcomes over time.

Incorporating these recommendations can contribute to an education system where teachers are better equipped to foster improved student academic achievement, leading to a more successful and impactful learning experience for students.

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